

COOKING PROCESS, SENSORY QUALITY AND NUTRITIONAL VALUES OF ARTISANAL AND COMMERCIAL CHAKHCHOUKHA

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Özet

Bu çalışmada, makarnalık buğday ve glutensiz unun endüstriyel ve ev yapımı chakhchoukha'sının mutfak kalitesi, pişirme sırasında yağ ilavesinin bu kaliteye etkisi incelenmiştir.

Bu amaca ulaşmak için, mutfak kalitesini karakterize ettiğimiz 7 endüstriyel chakhchoukha numunesi ve 4 üretilmiş ev yapımı chakhchoukha numunesi topladık. 2 çeşit yağ kullandık: ayçiçek yağı, bitkisel margarin. Mutfak kalitesinin değerlendirilen parametreleri şunlardır: pişirme süresi, şişme, sertlik, yapışkanlık ve pişme kaybı.

Makarnalık buğday irmiğinden yapılan zanaatkar chakhchoukha'nın verimi, glutensiz undan yapılan zanaatkar chakhchoukha'dan daha düşüktür.

Chakhchoukha kalitesi çalışması, ev yapımı chakhchoukha'nın endüstriyel chakhchoukha'ya kıyasla aşırı pişmeye karşı en büyük dirence sahip olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır. Öte yandan ev yapımı ürünlerden çok endüstriyel ürünlerde şişme görülmektedir. Ayrıca endüstriyel ürünlerde ev yapımı ürünlere göre daha fazla pişirme kaybı görülmektedir.

Yağın chakhchoukha'nın mutfak kalitesi üzerindeki etkisi ile ilgili olarak, eklenen yağ miktarındaki artışla chakhchoukha'nın optimal pişirme süresi azalır. Ayrıca, yağın chakhchoukha şişmesi üzerinde olumsuz bir etkisi vardır. Duyusal sonuçlar, yağın yapışkanlık ile negatif ilişkili olduğunu göstermektedir. Ancak sertlik ve pişirme kaybı ile önemli ölçüde ilişkili değildir.

Bu nedenle, zanaatkar chakhchoukha'nın mutfak özellikleri, endüstriyel chakhchoukha'nınkinden açıkça daha yüksektir. Pişirme sırasında eklenen yağın chakhchoukha şişmesi üzerindeki olumsuz etkisine rağmen, bu maddenin eklenmesi ev yapımı ve endüstriyel chakhchoukha'nın mutfak kalitesinde iyileştirici bir rol oynar.

Anahtar kelimeler: chakhchoukha, verim, yağ, mutfak kalitesi, pişirme süresi, şişme, sertlik, yapışkan, pişirme kaybı.

Abstract

In the present work, we studied the culinary quality of industrial and homemade chakhchoukha of durum wheat and gluten free flour, the effect of the fat addition during cooking on this quality.

To achieve this objective, we collected 7 samples of industrial chakhchoukha and 4 manufactured samples of homemade chakhchoukha on which we characterized their culinary quality. We used 2 fat types: sunflower oil, vegetable margarine. The evaluated parameters of the culinary quality are: cooking time, swelling, firmness, sticky and cooking loss.

The yields of artisanal chakhchoukha made from durum wheat semolina are lower than artisanal chakhchoukha made from gluten-free flour.

The study of chakhchoukha quality reveals that the homemade chakhchoukha has the greatest resistance to the overcooking compared to the industrial chakhchoukha. On the other hand, swelling appears at the industrial products rather than the homemade products. In addition, cooking loss is more observed at the industrial products than at the homemade products.

Concerning the influence of the fat on the culinary quality of chakhchoukha, the optimal cooking time of chakhchoukha decreases with the increase in the amount of added fat. Also, the fat has a negative impact on the chakhchoukha swelling. The sensory results show that the fat is negatively correlated with sticky. But, it is not significantly correlated with firmness and cooking loss.

Therefore, the culinary properties of the artisanal chakhchoukha are clearly higher than those of the industrial chakhchoukha. In spite of the negative impact of the added fat during cooking on the chakhchoukha swelling, the addition of this substance plays an improving role in culinary quality of the homemade and industrial chakhchoukha.

Keywords: chakhchoukha, the yield, fat, culinary quality, cooking time, swelling, firmness, sticky, cooking loss

1. INTRODUCTION

In Algeria, cereals are the staple food of households (Harrag and Boulfred 2019). According to Adel et al. (2015): an Algerian eats a pasta-based dish once a week. Dry pasta is a big part of our culinary traditions and we note that the production and consumption of this indigenous pasta is a very old habit in almost the whole country (Kezih et al., 2014). Indeed, home-prepared

pasta dishes are constituent elements of national identity that are important to safeguard and enhance (Cheriet, 2017). The Algerian food culture brings together a great diversity of these preparations. And that each of them has an anchorage, a particular color and flavor, and above all an ancestral manufacturing process, considered an art (well mastered on a domestic scale) rather than a science (Brahimi2014; Chemache et al ., 2018; Baouali et al., 2020).

Algeria is distinguished by a vast culinary heritage, we cite for example: vermicelli-type pasta recipes, called *rechta* which represents a preparation of filiform fresh pasta served in the manner of couscous by covering them with a meat stew after steaming them. Still in Algeria, there are also graniform pastes called *berkoukés* which is literally translated as lead. This pasta, which is made of fine semolina and water (or *tchichafrick*: cracked wheat), has the shape of small balls the size of a pea, obtained by rolling the moistened semolina in the manner which we make the couscous. And finally one of the "star" products of our regions is *chakhchoukha* (from the Berber chaoui, *chakhchoukha*, which means "to crumble"), it is essentially a festive dish consisting of crumbled semolina dough, however, differences in shape exist from one region to another and from one manufacturer to another (Kezih et al., 2014; Serventi 2014; Chandra and Jain 2017; Zaroual et al., 2019).

Chakhchoukha (from the Berber chaoui, *chakhchèkh* = crumble) is essentially a festive dish consisting of crumbled semolina dough, however there are differences in shape from one region to another and from one manufacturer to another. In recent years, the traditionally prepared product (ethnic) has begun to be consumed less than the profile of the industrial product. This can be explained by the gradual decline of traditional practices due to the complexity of the stages of preparation and lack of know-how.

1.1. Problematic and objective

Despite the progress made on an industrial scale, reproducing the quality of traditional pasta (Guezlane and Senator 1985. Guezlane et al., 1986; Doukani 2015) in general and that of *chakhchoukha* in a special way remains a challenge for producers. industrial. Thus, the tendency to consume industrial varieties is often accompanied by their disqualification compared to traditional products. Take the example of couscous where the work of Mezroua, (2011) and Zairi (2016) attest that the culinary properties of the artisanal product are clearly superior to those of industrial couscous.

Despite the large number of research works that have made it possible to better valorize the different Algerian local products, few scientific and technical works have discussed the manufacturing process and the different characteristics of *chakhchoukha*.

To this end, our contribution through this work is part of a preliminary study, the objective of which is to study the differences between industrial and traditional *chakhchoukha* on the one hand, and to assess the quality of *chakhchoukha*, produced by different industrial processes on the other hand.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Sampling

The study material consists of 11 batches of *chakhchoukha* distributed as follows

1) Four (04) artisanal lots (thin and medium):

- Two (02) based on durum wheat semolina
- Two (02) made from gluten-free flour

2) Seven (07) batches of industrial type available on the market in the eastern region of Algeria

Figure 1: medium artisanal

Figure 2: thin artisanal *chakhchoukha*.

2.2. Yield determination:

The yield of the traditional *chakhchoukha* process is determined by weighing the pre-cooked dry *chakhchoukha* (thin, medium) using a technical scale.

$R = [\text{mass of dry precooked } chakhchoukha \times 100] / [\text{mass of coarse and fine semolina used}]$.

A: Yield.

Figure 3: Mass of durum wheat semolina, gluten-free flour and dry precooked chakhchoukha (thin and medium artisanal *chakhchoukha*)

2.3. Cooking times:

A stopwatch is used to determine the cooking time, the latter is counted from the appearance of water vapor on the surface of the *chakhchoukha* according to the study carried out by MEZROUA (2011).

Cooking times can be categorized into:

A. Minimum time: is determined visually, when the flow of steam appears on the surface of the *chakhchoukha* then during the first cooking.

B. Optimum time: is counted by adding the cooking times (first and second or even third cooking).

C. Overcooking time (maximum): It is counted by adding the cooking times (third and fourth cooking).

2.4. Swelling index

The swelling provides information on the water absorption capacity of cooked pasta. A sample of 100 ± 0.01 g of dry *chakhchoukha* is poured into a 200 ml graduated cylinder containing 50

ml of water. The test tube is clogged. 10 successive reversals are carried out so as to properly hydrate all the particles. 50 ml of water are added to bring down the particles that have stuck along the wall. The test tube sealed and placed in a vertical position in a water bath at a temperature of 95°C, then the volume of the *chakhchoukha* is noted after 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55 and 60 min (Mezroua 2011). The swelling (S) is determined according to the relationship: The swelling of the dough during cooking SI is calculated by the difference between the weight of the dough before and after cooking).

$$SI (\%) = 100 \times (fV - iV) / iV$$

- fV: final volume

- iV: initial volume

2.5. Effect of the doses of fat on the optimal cooking time

To show the influence of fat on the cooking time, we used the doses of 2 ml, 4 ml, 6 ml, 8 ml for sunflower oil and the quantities of 2 g, 4 g, 6 g, and 8g for vegetable margarine and butter, for 100g of dry *chakhchoukha*. The cooking of the *chakhchoukha* was carried out with steam in a couscoussier and the addition of the fat is made after the second hydration and before the second cooking.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Yield determination:

The yield of the artisanal process, expressed in grams of dry *chakhchoukha*/100 g of semolina, increases according to the swelling of the *chakhchoukha*. It is 56.9% for the fine *chakhchoukha* and 59.8% for medium *chakhchoukha*. The yield of *chakhchoukha* for 100 g of gluten-free flour is 94.5% for fine *chakhchoukha* and 84% for medium *chakhchoukha*.

Figure 4: Yield of artisanal *chakhchoukha*

3.2. Cooking time

For each variety of *chakhchoukha*, we carried out 4 firings in order to confirm the time necessary to have the texture appreciated by the tasters.

In all the industrial varieties the optimum time is represented by the time of the first and second cooking. Except for the gluten-free variety where we need only one cooking for 4 min because at the second, and third or fourth cooking the dough becomes sticky

Table 1

Comparison of the averages of the optimal time and the overcooking time of artisanal *chakhchoukha*.

type	sample	1st cooking	2end cooking	Optimal time	3rd cooking	4th cooking	overcooking
durum wheat semolina	(A) thin <i>chakhchukha</i> .	20 min	15 min	35 min	8min	4 min	35 min + 12 min
	(B) medium <i>chakhchukha</i> .	15 min	10 min	25 min	6 min	3 min	25 min + 9 min
gluten free flour	(a) thin <i>chakhchukha</i> .	15 min	10 min	25 min	6 min	4 min	25 min + 10 min
	(b) medium <i>chakhchukha</i> .	12 min	8 min	20 min	5 min	3min	20 min + 8 min

Table 2

Comparison of the averages of the optimal time and the overcooking time of industrial varieties of *chakhchoukha*.

sample	1st cooking	2end cooking	Optimal time	3rd cooking	4th cooking	overcooking
Sample 001	14 min	14 min	28 min	10 min	3 min	41 min
Sample 002	12 min	14 min	26 min	10 min	3 min	39 min
Sample 003	17 min	16 min	33 min	12 min	4 min	49 min
Sample 004	16 min	15 min	31 min	11 min	4 min	46 min
Sample 005	15 min	15 min	30 min	10 min	3 min	43 min
Sample 006	17 min	16 min	33 min	12 min	4 min	49 min
Sample 007(gluten free flour)	4 min	0 min	4 min	0 min	0 min	0 min

3.3. Swelling index

Artisanal chakhchoukha made from durum wheat semolina have a higher water absorption capacity than artisanal chakhchoukha made from gluten-free flour. For the industrial varieties we noticed that the Samples: 001, 002 and 005 have a higher swelling index than the rest of the samples. The difference in the swelling of the shakhchukha between the different samples may be due to the composition of the raw material, Sasaki et al. (2002) noted that the swelling capacity of wheat starch is negatively correlated with amylose content.

Table 3

Swelling index of artisanal *chakhchukha* during cooking

type	Echantillon	IV	FV	SI (%)
durum wheat semolina	(A) thin <i>chakhchukha</i>	100g	240g	58
	(b) medium <i>chakhchukha</i> .	100g	235g	57
gluten free flour	(a) thin <i>chakhchukha</i>	100g	192g	47
	(b) medium <i>chakhchukha</i> .	100g	171g	41

Table 4

Swelling index of industrial *chakhchukha* during cooking

échantillon	IV	FV	SI (%)
Sample 001	100g	280g	64
Sample 002	100g	250g	60
Sample 003	100g	170g	40
Sample 004	100g	190g	47
Sample 005	100g	260g	60
Sample 006	100g	195g	48
Sample 007 (gluten free flour)	100g	171g	41

3.4. Effect of the doses of fat on the optimal cooking time

The results made it possible to determine the intensity of the following characters: shiny, smooth and oily according to the doses of added fat. We find that the intensity of these three characteristics (shiny, smooth and oily) increase with the increase in the dose of added fat. Moreover, we do not notice any differences between the effect of different fats (oil, vegetable margarine, butter) on chakhchoukha with regard to the characters previously considered.

The sensory analyzes carried out through the preference test show that the tasters preferred the shakhchoukha treated with doses of 6 ml / 100 g and 8 ml / 100 g for sunflower oil, and 6 g / 100 g and 8 g / 100 g for margarine vegetable and butter respectively.

The optimal cooking time of chakhchoukha is clearly influenced by the addition of fat, it decreases significantly with the increase in the dose of added fat. The decrease in the optimal cooking time with the use of fat may be due to the properties of fatty substances, including heat transfer, which accelerates the gelatinization of starch and consequently the cooking of chakhchoukha (Namoune et al. (2004).

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Further research seems necessary to complete the results of the present study. In-depth physico-chemical studies remain interesting to determine the differences in the nutritional value that could exist between the different types of *chakhchoukha* (industrial and artisanal)

5. BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

1. **Adel B., Agli, A.N.Touati D, OulamaraH. (2015).** Effet des caractéristiques socioéconomiques des ménages sur la consommation alimentaire *Résumés des présentations aux JFN de Marseille 2015 / Nutrition clinique et métabolisme 30 (2016) 109–132.*
2. **Baouali Ratiba, Baziz Amel, Hadjiedj Ali (2020)** La Préservation Du Patrimoine Gastronomique Algérien Levier Pour Le Développement Du Tourisme Durable El' Bahith volume 12, Numéro 2, Pages 153-153.
3. **Brahimi Fatima (2014).** Pâte traditionnelle algérienne aux épinards « typeMKARTFA » Mémoire de Magister en Sciences Alimentaires, Université Constantine 1. 123P.

4. Chandra S., Jain A.K. (2017) Foundations of Ethnobotany (21st Century Perspective) Scientific publishers 113-114pp.
5. **Chemache Loucif, Farida Kehal, Hacene Namoune, Makhoul Chaalal, Mohammed Gagaoua (2018)** Couscous: Ethnic making and consumption patterns in the Northeast of Algeria L. Journal of Ethnic Foods (5) 211-219
6. **Cheriet F., (2017).** La valorisation des produits de terroir en Algérie : démarches en cours, contraintes institutionnelles et perspectives. *Working Paper UMR MOISA 2017-2*
7. **Doukani K. (2015).** Etude comparative entre le couscous industriel et le couscous à base de glands Nature Technol;(13) :2.
8. **Guezlane L., Senator A. (1985)** Physicochemical and technological study of two types of couscous (artisanal and industrial). Ann Inst Natl Agron El Harrach Alger;5(1):47e62.
9. **Guezlane L, Selselet-Attou G., Senator A. (1986).** Comparative study of industrial and artisanal couscous. Cereal Ind; 43:25e9.
10. **Harrag Masbah., Boulfred Youssef (2019).** La sécurité alimentaire en Algérie Une étude analytique sur les céréales. Revue de l'économie financière et des affaires. Volume 03/ Numéro 02 / p162-188.
11. **Kezih R., Bekhouche F. and Merazka A. (2014)** Some traditional Algerian products from durum wheat African Journal of Food Science Vol. 8(1), pp. 30-34
12. **Mezroua Lyamine (2011).** Etude De La Qualité Culinaire De Quelques Couscous Industriels Et Artisanaux Et Effet D'adjonction De La Matière Grasse Durant La Cuisson. Mémoire de Magister en Sciences Alimentaires. Université Mentouri Constantine 139P.
13. **Namoune H., Kezih R., Feliachi K., Guerfi N. et Hamza N., (2004)** .L'effet de l'utilisation de certaines graisses pendant le processus de cuisson sur la qualité du chakhchoukha, Quatrième Conférence Scientifique des Sciences Agricoles, Assiout, Egypte
14. **Sasaki T., Yasui T., Matsuki J. et Satake T., (2002).** Comparison of physical properties of wheat starch gels with different amylose content. Cereal Chem. Vol.79.P :861–866.
15. **Serventi Silvano (2014)** Les pâtes La pensée de midi ACTES SUD pp.68-71
16. **Zaroual H., Boughattas F., Karoui R. (2019)** Traditional Foods in Maghreb: Production and Research Progress 51-113pp. In: Al-Khusaibi M., Al-Habsi N., Shafiur Rahman M. (eds) Traditional Foods. Food Engineering Series. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-24620-4_4

17. **Zairi Mohamed (2016).** Caractérisation De La Production De Quelques Lignées D'orge Issues De La Première Sélection Participative En Algérie. *Thèse De Doctorat En Sciences* Université DjillaliLiabes. Sidi Bel Abbas 171p